

Recent Variation/Advancement and Changes in Asian Rhinoplasty and a comparative study with Non-Asian population

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ABSTRACT

Background and Aim: Rhinoplasty is highly popular in both the East and the West. However, due to the differences in anatomy and culture between the East and the West, the rhinoplasty has different connotations in the East and the West. This study intends to explore the differences of rhinoplasty between Asian population and non-Asian population, and report the new progress of rhinoplasty for Asian population, and provide reference for clarifying rhinoplasty techniques which is suitable for Asian population.

Method: PubMed was searched in December 2020 attempting to find all articles describing Rhinoplasty in Asians and Non-Asians from April 2003 to December 2020. The Search terms used were "rhinoplasty in Asians" or "rhinoplasty in Caucasians" or "rhinoplasty in "Asian-Americans" or "rhinoplasty" or "rhinoplasty variations". The reference lists of identified papers were searched for further leads. The search results were sorted out and selected papers that provided comprehensive technical description of rhinoplasty procedures in different populations were included for further review. We excluded single case reports and non-English-language articles to facilitate the review process.

Results: Fifty-three articles meet the inclusion criteria and were included in this study. The literature shows that European population prefers smaller noses, while Asian populations have the opposite. The nose structure and preferences of Middle Eastern population are significantly different from the other two. This requires the surgeon to fully communicate with the patient before the operation and carefully evaluate the patient's nasal anatomical characteristics and the patient's own preferences, and be ready for anticipatory management.

Conclusions: In comparison to rhinoplasty for white people, dorsal augmentation using alloplastic implants is more common in Asian. Multi-layer cartilage tip grafting, modified vertical dome division and simple nose tip grafting are of great value to the improvement of Asian nose tips. In Asian rhinoplasty, the treatment of crooked nose, humps, and nasal septum requires careful attention. The anatomical characteristics of the patient's nose and face must be carefully explored.

Keywords: Rhinoplasty; Rhinoplasty in Asian; Asian in West; Technique of Rhinoplasty; Variation of Rhinoplasty

Introduction

The continent of Asia is the largest continent in the world. More than half of the world's population, from many different ethnic groups, is living there. Although many countries use the term "Asian" referring to

humans dwelling on that continent, in reality, Asian generally refers to peoples of East, Southeast, and South Asia. Inhabitants of Southwest Asia, which includes Arabs and Iranians, are more commonly designated as Middle Easterners. The term Asian as used in this text refers to people from Asia who has a Mongoloid background (Chinese, Japanese, Koreans, Vietnamese, Filipinos, Indonesians, and others). East Asia has a populace generally of Malay descent. The noses are generally small with voluminous thick skin, low dorsum, wide and striking ala, retracted premaxilla, and bulbous tip [1-4]. The surgical strategies of rhinoplasty for those styles of noses are awesome from the American/Western/Hispanic. The following are normally needed: dorsal augmentation, counter rotation and projection of the tip, and ultimately correction of striking ala and alar flare/base. A range of non-Caucasian rhinoplasty latest research have centered upon Asian or “Oriental” rhinoplasty [5-7]. Some have even cited it as a “Mongoloid” rhinoplasty and few have centered at the Asian-American nose, which includes capabilities consultant of loads of Asian countries, which includes China, Japan, Korea, the Philippines, Thailand, and Vietnam. This article will overview diverse sides of Asian rhinoplasty vs. Non-Asian rhinoplasty (American/Western/ Hispanic) after which decide not unusual place surgical strategies which have widespread software to this unique populace of patients.

With over 1.5 billion people and a long and complex history South Asia is a diverse region. Over the past 50,000 years, a multitude of different cultural and ethnic groups have migrated and settled in the region. The earliest known inhabitants were those of the Indus Valley civilizations of Harappa and Mohenjo-Daro, which date as far back as 5000 Bce. Multiple waves of migrations from the Caucasus by Indo-European-speaking peoples, and violent invasions by the Persian and Central Asian Empire. Over the course of the centuries, this intermingling of peoples has contributed to a vast amount of morphologic diversity, and it is impossible to define a “typical” Asian nose. For example, many inhabitants of the northeastern Indian states have anatomical features and linguistic features in common with Southeast Asia, whilst the languages and morphologic features of northwestern India and Pakistan often have much in common with Persia or the Middle East [8-13]. It should be noted that several authors have found differences in nasal morphology between North American Caucasians and Indians or South Asians [15]. For example, Patil et al. found that on average Indian women have greater nasal width, nasal length, and smaller nasolabial angle and tip projection. In addition, in our experience, there are certain common features of the Indian nose that differentiate it from the Caucasian nose: thicker skin, darker pigmentation, and weaker upper and lower lateral cartilages [16, 17]. Patient satisfaction and improved quality of work is the primary goal of Rhino plastic treatment.

Rhinoplasty for Asian noses is extensively unique from that for white noses. As rhinoplasty becomes highly popular among Asian people, it is important that the rhinoplasty surgeons master relevant anatomy and become skilled in necessary techniques to serve this segment of the population. A study of the Asian-American nose shows that while we have preferred to categorize the Asian-American nose (which is difficult because of variation within Asian national groups as well as within each group), Asian-American rhinoplasty is a procedure that involves vertical increase and, sometimes, large decrease.

Materials and methods

Nasal Anatomic differences between Asians and White

Although there are anatomic variations among different Asian populations, most Asians have noses with thicker skin and a lower dorsum. Their nasal bones tend to be smaller in height and width compared with that of whites.^{1,9} The Asian nasal tip is usually under projected and lacking in definition due to abundant fibro fatty tissue, weaker lower lateral cartilages, and a short columellate. The nasolabial angle tends to be acute due to a retracted columellate and premaxillary hypoplasia. The alar lobules are thick, and the alar bases are usually wide. Finally, the radix in Asians usually is lower compared with that in whites [18-21].

Differences in Rhinoplasty between Asians and Whites

Although some Asians are candidates for a classic reduction rhinoplasty, the underlying anatomic differences dictate that the goals of rhinoplasty in most Asians are different from those in whites [22]. The key components in most Asian rhinoplasties are augmentation of the nasal dorsum and tip [23]. Each patient seeks a different degree of nasal “refinement.” Therefore, the preoperative consultation is vital for the surgeon to properly understand the patient’s vision of the final result. Sometimes, there may be a language barrier which further complicates the matter. Finally, many Asians may be reluctant to overtly state their wishes as this may be in conflict with their cultural beliefs. To fully understand the patient’s desires, many experienced surgeons ask the patient to bring in photographs of models or refer to their own collection of preoperative and postoperative photographs. Computer imaging may also aid communication.

Common Surgical techniques used for Asian noses versus non-Asian noses:

There are certain anatomical features that seem to be common to most Indian noses (as compared with the Caucasian noses): greater pigmentation, thick skin, and weak cartilages. These characteristics have implications for the surgical techniques that are used in an Indian rhinoplasty. Most Asian noses are characterized by thick skin with abundant subcutaneous fiber fatty tissue, a weak cartilaginous framework, short nasal bones, underdeveloped anterior nasal spine, and small quadrilateral septal cartilage. meanwhile, there are individual variations. The associated cutaneous findings include a wide and under projected dorsum, a low radix and nasion, a nasal tip that is bulbous, lacking definition, under projected, and either ptotic or over rotated (short nose); with a short columella and an alar base that is wide and flaring.

Low Nasal Dorsum for Asian patients with a low nasal dorsum, there may be consensus that dorsal augmentation is necessary. However, the augmentation approach remains arguable and for most part is geographically related. Worldwide, silicone implants or a few different sort of alloplastic material is used in the majority of Asian rhinoplasties. This is because of the reality that most Asian rhinoplasties are carried out in Asia and with unique exceptions; surgeons in Asia feel cushiest the usage of alloplastic for dorsal augmentation.

In Europe, majority of surgeons select autogenous augmentation and shun alloplastic substances in the nostril because of its associated complications (infection, displacement, extrusion, and capsular contracture). Although complications are less common with auto grafts, many proponents of alloplastic augmentation had been capable of produce favorable outcomes with an acceptable complication rate by modifying their method and cautious patient selection. They further cite the downside of autogenous augmentation (limited donor material, donor site morbidity, extended operative time, resorption, and warping) Alloplasts Alloplastic substances for dorsal augmentation include silicone, expanded polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), and porous polyethylene(Medpor

Silicon implant augmentation

It is the most commonly used per-PTFE sheets and usually thin as compared to silicone implants, making them more suitable for minor augmentation and tip projection improvement. While a supratip break is rarely required, it is incredibly discreet in contrast to what western surgeons are used to. As compared to Caucasian patients, another significant distinction is the almost universal request for a complete infratip lobule that needed to be cut into the correct form. Sheet stacking is needed for large augmentations. In Asia and ciates, Flagstaff, AZ, Gore-Tex (polytetrafluoroethylene; W.L. Gore & Asso-formed method of augmentation rhinoplasty in Asia and ciates) is also common. Silicone implants are common for a variety of reasons: cosmetic outcomes are usually superior to autologous augmentation in Asians, implants are cheap, the treatment is straightforward, there is no donor-site morbidity, risks are low, and it does not cut bridges for salvage autologous rhinoplasty in the event of complications. As a consequence, for Asian rhinoplasty, implant rhinoplasty is the chosen form. A patient requiring an autologous rhinoplasty, failed implant rhinoplasty, a short nose, and correction of extreme nasal deformity (such as congenital malformations and painful

deformities) are both reasons for autologous rhinoplasty.

Polytetrafluoroethylene Augmentation

Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE; Carnage Tax) has been broadly utilized for dorsum or potentially tip expansion in quit selling Violence Tex inserts for the plastic medical procedure in Koreas well as in China. There are no authority elective suppliers for the occasion. Rhinoplasty procedures utilizing PTFE for tip enlargement are regularly alluded to as a "Korean-style rhinoplasty.' PTEF normally comes as sheets that should be cut into a legitimate shape. PTEF sheets frequently slim the difference with silicone embeds and may accordingly be more valuable for little expansion. Bigger enlargements may require stacking of sheets.

Silicon implant augmentation

Silicon implant augmentation is commonly considered to provide the best cosmetics results in Asians. There are several debates concerning which shape of implant can achieve the best aesthetic/cosmetics results. There are two general shapes of nasal implants which are I-shaped and L-shaped. The dorsum is often supplemented by classic I-shaped implants. Surgeons who currently use them usually perform a concomitant tip-plasty to enhance tip projection. Some I-shaped implants also have a tip extension. Implants are placed subperiosteally on the nasal dorsum and act as cantilever grafts to augment the dorsum and support tip projection. However, these implants are relatively soft and are generally thought to provide less support for the tip than L-shaped implants as a columellar extension is absent. Cartilage grafting over the implant tip can also be used to provide more tip.

Autogenous augmentation

The use of diced cartilage in dorsal augmentation has been periodically documented in the literature as early as 1943 with the aid of using Peer, in 1951 by Cottle, and in 1968 by Burian, eleven though it did not gain wide-spread acceptance. Guerrerosantos revisited this idea and refining the method by wrapping fragmented cartilage in fascia, while Erol brought a bigger audience with his description of wrapping diced cartilage in Surgical in 2000. Modifications have been variously described, in the idea of using diced cartilage as the building block for dorsal augmentation, particularly adding assorted tissue adhesives to ease shaping of the graft, changing the material wrapping the cartilage, or completely foregoing an encasement. Diced cartilage with fascia represents a potentially best graft for dorsal augmentation, as it makes use of the lower complication rates associated with autologous grafts. It also provides a graft that has the capacity to recreate dorsal aesthetic lines in a natural and predictable manner.

Rhinoplasty in Hispanic patients

Hispanic culture of Portugal or Spain and, belong to, or being a person of Latin American descent living in the south American continent; especially: one of Cuban, Mexican, or Puerto Rican origin). A recent published study by the American Society of Plastic Surgeons (ASPS) in March 2008 reports a 15% increase in cosmetic surgery among ethnic patients. Compared with the ASPS data published in 2000, cosmetic surgery among Hispanics has increased by 173% with rhinoplasty among the top procedures requested. The 2007 ASPS national clearing house data on cosmetic demographics indicate Hispanics as the second most popular group requesting cosmetic surgery with 1,011,071 patients; only behind Caucasians. It is imperative for cosmetic doctors to become familiar with the Hispanic nose and its different archetypes. Hispanic rhinoplasty is not a novel subject and Rollin, et al have previously described and classified the Hispanic nose.

Daniel classified the Hispanic nose into four major types: type one, Castilian; type two, Mexican American; type three, Mestizo; type four, Creole. These three “archetypes” dictate the surgical techniques required for correction (rhinoplasty). The Type I noses can often be corrected simply by dorsal reduction with minor tip and base modifications while Type II noses typically need dorsal augmentations with open rhinoplasty to address the tip using both suture techniques and tip grafts. The Type III noses have a significant vertical and horizontal disproportion. This requires correction with reduction of the wide nasal base in conjunction with dorsal augmentation and finally, an in-depth discussion regarding the patient's surgical goal is very important patient wants to obtain an aesthetically pleasing result while maintaining ethnicity or whether the patient wants to have a nose that appears like Caucasian.

Discussion

Cosmetic enhancement of the Asian nose requires a completely unique philosophical technique and approach in comparison with the ones essential for Western rhinoplasty [24-27]. First, cultural motivations can be absolutely different. For instance, the Asian patient may prefer rhinoplasty for no particular purpose than that a larger nose may impart a better likelihood of accruing wealth. Second, the differences in cultural responses to beauty enhancement can be essential to recognize both for zero-generation Asian patients living in the West and later generations who have become more assimilated into a Western perspective. Third, a culturally sensitive technique that underscores preservation however enhancement of ethnic identity can be important in a good percentage of Asian patients seeking rhinoplasty. Cultural preservation has become the buzzword these days for lots Asians who preference cosmetic enhancement regardless of their global hemisphere of residence. Finally, the surgical technique for Asian rhinoplasty lies in diametric distinction to Western rhinoplasty, because the former is principally augmentative and the latter reductive in nature [27-33]. This article wills attention on each the cultural underpinnings that are mandatory in approaching the Asian patient in addition to operative approach that can cause a greater degree of consistency in aesthetic results for the Asian nose. A basic knowledge of rhinoplasty technique is assumed and isn't detailed herein besides for advanced ideas that differ from Occidental rhinoplasty. As mentioned, Asian rhinoplasty should be approached first with the aid of using expertise the patient earlier than understanding the operation.

We have discovered that in many Asian cases, the radix can fall approximately at the mid pupil, rather than the supratarsal crease, which might be a more acceptable dorsal height for white patients. A more conservative bridge height will accomplish the desired softening ethnic features while retaining a more ethnically acceptable look that, if lifted too high, could seem unnatural. The nasal tip contour may be gently augmented to retain the rounded form or more sculpted, depending on the patient's needs and what will look better for the individual's features based on aesthetic judgment. In a later part, various methods for achieving these looks will be discussed. Any prospective Asian patient will benefit from looking at photos of Asian models and examining a surgeon's "before-and-after" photographic findings. The caveats are obvious: the prospective patient could be more enamored with the composite of the Asian model's face rather than the nose (which would also be unattainable) and that looking at before-and-after results may be deceptive because everyone's morphology, especially for the nose, varies. It's also a bit of a stretch to assume that everyone is fully committed to preserving their race. The uniqueness with models with mixed race descent has been emphasized in today's globalized marketplace. In addition, as miscegenation rates increase, offspring from these mixed marriages may evolve a new ethnically blended aesthetic. Finally, I've noticed that Asians who are married to white people often attempt procedures to soften ethnic features in order to be more agreeable with their partners. In contrast, we find it fascinating that many whites search out Asians with ethnic features simply because they are drawn to those characteristics. Any aesthetic consultation should include a consideration of these motivations. Regardless of the reasons behind the patient's wishes, the surgeon must determine.

In summary, there has been a tremendous growth of cosmetic surgery among Asians worldwide. Rhinoplasty is second only to blepharoplasty in terms of popularity among Asians regarding cosmetic surgical procedures. Most Asians seek to improve their appearance while maintaining the essential features of their ethnicity. There

are considerable ethnic nasal and facial variations in this population alone. Successful rhinoplasty in Asians must take into account underlying anatomic differences between Asians and whites. Due to ethnic variations and cultural differences, careful preoperative counseling is necessary to align the patient's expectations with the limitations of the procedure. Because of the Asian nasal tip's innate qualities, including weak cartilages and abundant subcutaneous tissue, success with nasal tip procedures for Asians depends on the combined application of appropriate suturing, grafting, and defatting, with grafting techniques contributing the most. Augmenting nasal tip projection in Asians can be effectively achieved using autogenously cartilage grafts. Techniques to increase the tip projection are chosen based on the degree of the tip support and the amount of the tip projection desired. In the majority of Asian patients, structural onlay grafts with or without strengthening of tip support with a columellar strut can achieve successful results. The septal extension graft is a reliable and effective technique in patients who need a substantial augmentation of the tip when the tip support is poor.

Due to underlying anatomic differences the goals of rhinoplasty in most Asians are different from those in whites. Although there are exceptions, most Asian rhinoplasties require some augmentation of the nasal dorsum and tip. Because each patient seeks a different degree of nasal refinement, careful preoperative consultation is needed to understand the patient's vision of the final result and discuss the surgical goals as well as the limitations of the procedure.

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